

"TIME" AS A UNIVERSAL CONCEPT

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Annotation

The article analyzes the concept of "time" in the literature picture of the world. Time, like space, are universal categories of being, with the help of which a person perceives the world around him and creates a system of knowledge about the world. As a result, it is easy to explain the undying interest in the representation of the concept of "time" in the folklore text.

Keywords: ethno-linguistic picture of the world, ethnic temporal mentality, temporal universals, temporal meaning of the measure of time, worldview.

Time is a kind of link that connects a person with various aspects of life. Through the category of time-space, a dialogue is carried out between generations' people, cultural and historical eras, and the connection of one subject with another. Moreover, the very concept of a chronotope contains many meanings. It reflects mythological, religious-philosophical, scientific ideas about time and space, which in their chronotope are multicomponent system consisting of several levels. In the structure of this category, you can allocate private time-space, collective time-space, public time-space, generation time-space, etc. All of them are interconnected themselves and form a single complex whole. Respectively changes occurring at one of the levels entail changing the whole system. For example, rethinking spatial temporal relations by an individual gradually leads to a reassessment of this category by the team society.

Hence, the non-determinism of the system chronotope, the impossibility of predicting those waiting for it changes.

Moreover, the future, according to the researchers, is not always turns are embodied in works of literature. For in the present there is many options for further development of the considered events and phenomena. No man can accurately to say what his tomorrow will be, based on knowledge about day yesterday and today.

He only hypothesizes assumptions about the impending future, in which one of the probabilistic options is realized. Similarly, there are ideas about the past, says synergetic. Impossible to talk about him on the basis of knowledge about the accomplished future. For everything theories put forward will be hypothetical, especially when it comes to the very distant past.

Accordingly, the chronotope is not linear, but hierarchical structure. Time in it does not always move forward – from past to present and future. It is reversible and multidirectional. If depicted graphically, then the past will appear as a solid, branched line, the future is like a dotted line, branched line, the present is like a point connecting these lines. Hence the asymmetry between the past and the future.

According to supporters of the synergistic approach, no fundamental ontological difference between data three chronotopes. For the very concept of history is meaningless. Past, present and future are all present at the same time every moment of being. Perception of time-space depends on the choice of reference point. The same phenomenon can be presented as past, present and future in different coordinate systems. This understanding of the chronotope category led to distribution in synergetic of two approaches – historical and teleological. One of them is aimed at understanding the past, the other the future. The purpose of the historical approach is the study of space-time boundaries already past events and events that could be, but did not occur due to a number of circumstances and teleological. One of them is aimed at understanding the past, the other the future. The purpose of the historical approach is the study of space-time boundaries already past events and events that could be, but did not occur due to a number of circumstances. The task of teleology is consideration of chronotopes of phenomena that have not yet occurred. Both approach do not give an accurate description of the past and the future, and only speculate about the possible

development of events. Accordingly, the distinctive property of the chronotope is its probabilistic nature. Its levels, although interact with each other, but not always mutually condition each other. Past and present scientists believe that there might well not have been any events and some of them could cause completely different consequences in the future. Therefore, the central task synergetic - building all probabilistic models functioning of the chronotope in reality, in consciousness of the individual and society, in the structure of artistic works.

At present, there are several forms categories of time-space that are embodied in literature. First, the real chronotope, acting as essential component of reality characteristic of human being and becoming an object the writer's understanding. The chronotope that arises in the perception reader in the process of comprehending the text created image writer. Moreover, each of these forms is relative and is evolving system. So, the real chronotope is changing depending on the point of reference, the position of the observer. In a work of art reflects that facet of a given category, which is chosen by the perceiving subject in as the hence the keen interest of supporters synergistic approach to the forms of the chronotope, which are not were embodied in the work of a particular writer.

Building models that have not become an object of comprehension artist's words, researchers put forward hypotheses about possible ways of depicting reality in artistic whole. This approach makes it possible to deepen your understanding of the creative process. Time-space, transformed by the consciousness of the writer, is also an emerging, unstable system. In one transformed by the consciousness of the artist and reflected in work. Relativity is inherent in space-time coordinate system that develops in the mind of the reader. She varies depending on the historical era, national culture, social and age group to which belongs to the perceiving subject, his worldview and attitude, emotional state, level education, the degree of preparedness for a "dialogue" with the author, heroes, work. Therefore, the goal of synergy approach in the study of this model of the chronotope is reduced to identification of all variants of spatial-temporal systems that may arise in the minds of potential readers. The solution of this

problem allows us to build assumptions about the fate of a literary work, features of its interpretation. It is noteworthy that the very ideas about the time-space of a person and, accordingly, a writer are very conditional character. In an effort to know the category of the chronotope, the researchers say, people differentiate it into levels, enter units of measure. However, none of them does not know exactly what the actual structure of time-space is and whether it exists at all, whether it is possible measurement of time and space, or are they infinite, endless. Hence the spread in synergetic of the opinion about that the artistic chronotope is a self-organizing system. Its initial values are chaos and order. For at every stage of the historical development of society a certain concept of time and space is formed, based on the choice of one of the many variants of the theory of the existence of this category. It's in your the turn determines the relativity of the chronotope system. Her distinctive features are "changes», which, "being born in the processes of universal interaction, included in the way objects acquire dynamic stability under the pressure of continuously arising and transforming in their individuality and into inexhaustible combinations of factors of natural and social life", artistic creativity, trends literary process. Time-space has a contextual meaning. It is revealed in the process of studying all the components, organizing an artistic whole. Because depending on them combinations, the content of the chronotope changes. An example of this is river image. In works built in the genre of travel essay, it is only the embodiment of a reservoir inherent in one area or another. In a philosophical novel, a river associated with human life. In fairy tales, this image sometimes plays the role of a mirror helping the hero to look at yourself from the outside, etc. The specificity of the chronotope is influenced by the genre variety artistic work. Yes, time is space. historical novel is fundamentally different from the time-space of a fantasy novel. Time category in works, the plot of which is based on real events of the past, carries information about culture, life, national traditions of the depicted people. Through time-space reveals the author's attitude to the historical period he describes. Time fantasy novel contains ideas of convention being, the relativity of its boundaries. Hence, the need understanding the essence of literary genres, especially when the study

of artistic time-space in works that are a combination of several genres. For example, in the work of some modern writers in the structure of one novel, elements are used detective, science fiction, fairy tale, adventure, myth.

As a result, the semantic content of the chronotope the work acquires ambiguity. Distinctive features of the category of time-space become illusory, relativity, and non-linearity. Sometimes time is observed. Time in such works contains information about real and fictional events that, combined, form a special, a unique world where a fairy tale smoothly turns into a myth or turns into reality. Increasing importance spatial images, time periods, as in detective genre location of heroes, location surrounding objects, things, time interval actions taken play a fundamental role. Accordingly, the semantics of familiar phenomena expands. In modern hermeneutics, much attention is paid to chronotope of translated works. This is due to the fact that in them there is a combination of two spatial-temporal positions. The writer's chronotope is connected with translator's chronotope. As a result, they are superimposed aesthetic views, life experience, ideas about reality and the creative process. Hence the significant complicating the interpretation of artistic time and space. For the reader who does not know the original language, cannot give an accurate interpretation of the content of the category chronotope. His interpretation will cover more degrees of time-space, rethought through the prism consciousness of the translator. Thus, the artistic chronotope is difficult category. It is characterized by versatility and versatility. Hence the need to consider time-space through the prism of modern hermeneutics, semiotics, communication theory, synergetics, hierology. Using their achievements and methodology allows a deeper understanding of the essence of the chronotope, revealing its basic properties and qualities. Great value for disclosure features of artistic time-space has category of temporal rhythm, which has become the subject attention of scientists in recent decades.

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